

Sample 26a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0032
	{Si}	61.6
	{Al, Si}	7.8
	{Fe}	7.3
	{Si, Fe}	3.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.5
	{Al, Si, K}	2.1
	{Ca}	2.0
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.5
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.5
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.4
	{Na, Si}	1.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.8
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Cl}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Ti}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Cl}	0.4
	{S, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Zn-LA1}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

		area %
	Sinter	0.8
	Pellet	3.2
	Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.0
	Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
	Ore / hot metal	0.1
	BOF converter slag	0.6
	BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
	Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
	Desulph slag	0.0
	Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
	Blast furnace slag	0.0
	Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
	Olivine flux	0.0
	Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
	Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
	Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
	MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
	Tundish gunning mass	0.0
	Alumina	0.0
	Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
	Rich in Zn-compounds	0.3
	Fe-metal rich	0.2
	Coal and cokes or soil	9.7
	Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
	Carbon rich - other	3.1
	Cement or BOF converter	0.5
	Cement	3.0
	Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
	Ti-rich paint	0.0
	Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
	Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
	Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
	Salt or salt layer	0.0
	Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	55.2
	Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	20.0
	Misc silicates including natural	0.3
	Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
	Apatite	0.0
	Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.5
	Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
	Na-sulphate rich	0.0
	Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
	Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
	Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
	Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
	Unassigned other	0.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	5.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	1.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.3
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	9.7
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	3.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.5
Urban	3.1
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	55.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	20.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.3
Unknown	0.5
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 26b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0059
	{Si}	55.9
	{Al, Si}	8.9
	{Fe}	6.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.7
	{Si, Fe}	3.4
	{Ca}	2.5
	{Al, Si, K}	2.3
	{Si, Ca HiP}	2.1
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.6
	{Na, Si}	1.5
	{Na, Si, Cl}	1.1
	{Mg, Si}	0.9
	{Cl}	0.8
	{Cl}	0.6
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.6
	{Mg, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Si, Cl}	0.4
	{S, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Zn-LA1}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.1
Pellet	3.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	2.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.4
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.8
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	6.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
Carbon rich - other	2.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	5.7
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.3
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	48.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	24.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.4

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	5.5
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	1.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.8
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.8
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	6.5
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	2.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	6.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	48.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	24.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.4

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 26c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0296
	{Si}	56.1
	{Al, Si}	8.2
	{Fe}	6.7
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.5
	{Si, Fe}	3.4
	{Ca}	2.4
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.0
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.8
	{Al, Si, K}	1.8
	{Na, Si}	1.5
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.5
	{Na, Si, Cl}	1.2
	{Ti}	1.0
	{Cl}	0.8
	{Cl}	0.7
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.6
	{S}	0.6
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Si, Cl}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{S, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Zn-LA1}	0.2
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.8
Pellet	3.4
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.8
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.9
Desulph slag	0.1
Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.8
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	4.2
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.2
Carbon rich - other	1.0
Cement or BOF converter	1.1
Cement	5.7
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	1.5
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	50.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	24.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.4
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.4

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	6.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	2.2
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.3
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.8
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	4.2
Site - carbon-rich other	0.2
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	1.0
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.1
Urban	7.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	50.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	24.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.7
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.4

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels